

Using GUF_I in Data Management

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NCAR Computing Environment

The Data Management Problem

- Active Projects that involve Data Management
 - Archive Cooling Project
 - Purges
- NCAR has over 2B inodes
 - 1.6B in large file system (GPFS)
 - 120M in home space (GPFS)
 - 100M in Campaign Store (GPFS)
 - 250M in Archive (HPSS)
- Find, pfind are moderately fast for POSIX, not Archive
 - Take resources against POSIX or Archive
- How to uniformly search all spaces that are available
- Pilot Grand Unified File Index from Los Alamos National Laboratory
 - Follow POSIX permissions, open source, ease of use to setup and administer

How GUFi Works

1. GUFi reads **source** directory tree metadata in a variety of ways (e.g., walk tree, ingest a flat file, call the GPFS API, etc.)
2. It creates a **search** directory tree with the same directory structure, permissions, and ownership; each directory contains a database with metadata about the files in the original directory
3. The GUFi query commands access the **search** tree to quickly provide data (e.g., amount of bytes in a subdirectory, etc.).

How GUFi Works: Source and Search Trees

Challenges

- When starting out GUFU has not been in production anywhere yet
- NCAR has billions of files across many storage systems
- NCAR purges folder and directories on scratch
 - Some processes must be reworked to do this at scale
- Created a few processes
 - MPI based GPFS ILM Scanner
 - GPFS ILM Scan treewalk
 - GUFU flat file generator

Integration Details

- Supermicro NVMe box with 10 NVMe slots
- 2x 22 core Xeon Processor
- 768GB of RAM
- Storage components
 - RAM for queries and index process, 768GB
 - NV SSD capacity to store GUFIs trees, 4x750GB
 - RAID-0 for NVMe devices
- After initial ingest and post processing db is fixed backup GT
- Weekly index of storage system

NCAR GUFU Workflow

GLADE

Campaign Store

Data Management

NCAR HPSS Archive

Cluster Frontend

NCAR GUFU Workflow

NCAR GUFU Workflow

NCAR GUFi Workflow

1. Dump Inode Info

2. Treewalk

Data Management

3. Post Processing

NCAR HPSS Archive

Cluster Frontend

NCAR GUFU Workflow

- 1. Dump Inode Info
- 2. Treewalk

Data Management

- 3. Post Processing
- 4. Create GUFU index

Cluster Frontend

NCAR GUFU Workflow

Archive Cooldown Project

- Project goals: slow ingest to archive, move data to appropriate location and clean up unneeded data.
- Utilizing GUFi for single queries and complex queries
- Created precomputed summaries for common complex queries
 - These can be stored in a summary table in GUFi tree
- Example summarized query:

```
<directory> contains 12345 files distributed in 123 directories,  
owned by 4 users (list of users) and 6 projects for a grand total  
of 200TB
```

```
user u1 owns nnn files for a total of 10TB
```

```
(etc for the other users)
```

```
projects p1 has mmm files for a total of 20TB
```

```
(etc for the other projects)
```

Purge

- Purge timeframes
 - scratch, 4 months
 - projects, 1 year
 - Campaign Store, 5 years
- Users can query files that may be candidates for deletion/removal
- # `gufi_find -ctime -atime -mtime`
- This will give users a list of files to move to other spaces for longer retention
- Yes, we check for touches

POSIX/HPSS vs GUFU Equivalent

Task	POSIX	HPSS	GUFU
get space	du <path>	hsi du <path>	gufu_stats total-space <path>
find file	find <path> -name <file>	hsi find <path> -name <file>	gufu_find -name <file> <path>

Performance

	# files	du (native)	du (GUFU)	speedup	find (native)	find (GUFU)	speedup
Campaign Store	3.1M	9m20s	3.6s	155x	3m20s	9.8s	20.4x
GPFS	100K	2m49s	8.5s	19x	29.6s	6.9s	4.2x
HPSS	29M	174m8s	50s	208x	214m32s	5m12s	41x

How to get started

- Download source code and browse documentation:

<https://github.com/mar-file-system/GUFI>

- Contact us for any NCAR implementation specific questions at:

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